

PRIORITIZING INFORMATION SECURITY: ANALYSIS OF SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT LIFE CYCLE METHODOLOGIES USING THE NIST CYBERSECURITY FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

Information Security is now a major consideration for companies in protecting their data, customer's information, and sensitive areas. Besides from protecting data it is also becoming evident that in the past years that software development is being challenged by hackers and other personnel in the field of information technology with negative motives. Challenge now arises not on the final product or the capability of a software to withstand these threats and attacks, but the challenge is to protect itself during the development phase. SDLC or software development life cycles has proven its worth in developing timely and effective software. With the new trend and security issues it is forfeiting to analyze the capabilities of the majority of the SDLCs in terms of security. The study will analyze each SDLC, namely waterfall, rapid application development, spiral, v-model, and agile using the phases indicated in the NIST Cybersecurity SDLC Framework which focuses on security. The study focused on how each phase of the NIST framework can be used on each model and highlight how security is managed on each SDLC. It is not the goal of this study to determine which SDLC is better and which is not. The study aims to explain and describe how each SDLC implements and possibly use security features in each of its phase using the NIST as the framework of the study.

Keywords: *Information Security, Cybersecurity, Software Development Life Cycle, Waterfall, Rapid Application Development Model, V-Model, Spiral Model, Agile Model, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Software Engineering*

INTRODUCTION

Information Security was not an issue and was not used back in the late 1950s and 1960s, it was only realized in the 70s that from computer security it shifted to information security. The importance of security in the field of information technology was truly recognized due to the fact that threats, vulnerabilities exist and needs to be addressed in different ways possible. The merging of viruses that attacks local computers, network of devices, and enterprise systems be it in the government and in the corporate is something that needs to be addressed and must taken account for. Cases of data breach have been reported to escalate in the millennium year due to the open internet and the rise of technological convergence. This raises issues and challenges for software developers on how to develop well designed and up to date software without taking the data and information of the users in the pedestal of risk to hackers. SDLCs have proven their worth in guiding the team and serving as an important framework of the development. The challenge for SDLC now is to integrate information security measures in the process of software development. This study used the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Cybersecurity SDLC Framework (Revision 02) in analyzing each SDLC and how the framework can be injected on each phase or combined phases.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to analyze the five major software development life cycles (SDLC) through the use of literary review. With the use of the chosen methodology the researcher has provided definition, advantages, and disadvantages of the use of each SDLC. From this description the researcher was able to identify the security measures that can be integrated on each or combined phases of each model. The research used the NIST Cybersecurity Model which has five areas namely, (1) initiation, (2) acquisition or development, (3) implementation or assessment, (4) operations or maintenance, and (5) sunset/ disposal. The study does not in any way suggest the best and worst SDLC, rather the study described the best way possible how each model can integrate the use of information security to address the possible threats, attacks, and vulnerabilities that negative entities oppose.

Review of Pertinent Literature

NIST Cybersecurity Software Development Life Cycle

In an article published by the National Institute of Standards and Technology written by Radack, S. (2009) it provides a new understanding on the general phases of SDLCs. The published work features five phases of the life cycle which are initiation, acquisition, implementation or assessment, operations or maintenance, and sunset (disposal). These phases highlights security in software development which is the main reason of choosing the NIST's framework as security is one of the top issues in the field of information technology today. Also, NIST has paved the way for information security to be injected in software life cycles the institution also provided a way to assess the risk, manage threats,

and accountability in project managers or anyone leading any software development project. According to Radack (2009), the new SDLC framework was developed in the NIST by Richard Kissel, Kevin Stine, and Matthew Scholl. The phases shall be the basis for the review of the five models stated at the start of the study.

Comparison of SDLC

Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) is defined by Gupta, A., et al (2021) as a method where there is a clear goal of procedure in developing high end quality software which are economic to produce. SDLC must always be viewed as a systematic and logical approach to system development, testing, quality assurance, and implementation. In their study a comparison was made to determine the advantages and weaknesses of each SDLC. The study focused on determining when to use each SDLC – in simple or complex projects. The study revealed in descriptive research the definitions, usage, advantages, limitations, and strengths of each SDLC that was commonly used in industries.

Software Engineering

According to the study conducted by Akinsola, J., et al (2020) software engineering and software development life cycle are not two different entity rather SDLC is a major part of software engineering when it comes to system development. In their journal software engineering was described as a meticulous process of coding and writing efficient codes in order to produce economical and high quality software and the use of SDLC provides an avenue for one. That is the reason why an analysis of the different SDLCs must be conducted in order to assess each model's value and how they can contribute to the advancement of software quality and security. By analyzing these models' other researches as similar to Akinsola and others provide improvement with the use of SDLC in contributing to high quality, economic, and marketable programs.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized existing studies and literature to develop the ideas and information presented. Sources of studies and literature came from legitimate and indexed journals. Studies revolving in software development lifecycle and the NIST Cybersecurity framework were meticulously analyzed and studied by the researcher to come up with the final objective of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

WATERFALL MODEL

A waterfall model starts with determining the requirements through analysis and planning, followed by the designing of the system or software then implementing the system for testing and quality assurance, then followed by the integration of the system in the process of the organization it also involves a deeper process of testing and eventually is fully implemented, operated and maintained. This method is a linear process of software development without considering such as changes, market demands, and business requirements (Saravanos, 2023)

In an analysis conducted by Pargaonkar, S. (2023), he has provided the advantages and disadvantages of using the waterfall model which are the following:

Advantages of Waterfall

1. Structured and Predictable
2. Comprehensive Documentation
3. Easy Management
4. Clear Deliverables
5. Suitable for Small Projects

Disadvantages of Waterfall

1. Limited Flexibility
2. Lack of Customer Involvement
3. High Risk
4. Lengthy Development Cycle
5. Not suitable for Complex Projects

Recommendation in Incorporating Information Security using the NIST Cybersecurity Framework

Initiation Phase: Since the first phase of the waterfall model involves the gathering of requirements that involves information and data it is best to integrate the concept of initiation that all information and data being collected and to be processed in the system adheres to the basic triad of information security, confidentiality, integrity, and accessibility. This means that the gathered data must be confidential especially when there are data that are highly valuable it is best to have an NDA or non-disclosure agreement between the developer and the company or organization. Another is the integrity. All information must be of credible source and must be treated with secrecy and use this information for system development purposes only, especially in the initiation phase where all information about the process and wants of the company is provided. It is important to remember that the information security protocols must be well stated and

fully implemented as this is a waterfall model where there should be a well-defined plan at the start.

Acquisition/ Development Phase: This phase may be done during the system design and implementation or coding as it involves risk assessment and creation of an information system plan where the developers consider information security protocols, hardware, network, and others in all parts of the software/ program that needs to be addressed. Since this is waterfall, all controls and procedures with regards to information security must be aligned to the previous determined requirements and the conduct of risk assessment involves only the system design and implementation.

Implementation/ Assessment Phase: Besides from the actual testing which involves quality assurance, information security must also be observed in the testing phase and implementation of the system. All use case studies and QA results must be well documented. Security in all forms of the modules must be considered not only the basic ones such as username and password, complex parts of the program must be considered on how information security is integrated from the software's modules, business process, framework used, network, and hardware adopted in the project. In a waterfall concept this phase can be made in the Testing and Deployment and should only be done in small scale and controlled variable projects.

Operations/ Maintenance Phase: After the successful creation and testing of the software, it will be maintained. During operational or maintenance phase, proper documentation must take place and change management must also take place as software or programs integrate new hardware, provide new features, and upgrading its firmware also change in environment may occur with this changes information security must assess the potential threats, attacks, and vulnerabilities. In the waterfall model to achieve a successful assessment it is advised to conduct this phase in the Deployment and Maintenance Phase to see the results of the deployment and to suggest possible steps in security.

Sunset/ Disposal Phase: The sunset phase or disposal phase involves the transition of the existing system to the proposed and developed system. This must ensure how data and information is transferred and if there are data that needs to be disposed, and what mode of retrieval is implemented. Since the waterfall model is a linear model it is suggested that this phase is conducted in the requirements gathering where information and data is gathered. A plan must be layout regarding the disposal of unwanted data from the present storage that is not relevant enough to be transferred, storage or archival of existing or old information, proper transfer of data and its methodology, also to consider is the hardware and peopeware. Security is much involve in this phase.

RAPID APPLICATION DEVELOPMENT (RAD) MODEL

Rapid Application Development (RAD) addresses the issues and challenges faced by the waterfall model in terms of change management. In the study of Sasmito, G., et al. (2020) it is described that RAD model focuses on quick software development and prototyping

that provides a quality software in the end of the process. Also, this model helps the economic part of the development and maintenance of the software. The difference of RAD with other models is that it has only short span of planning process and focuses more on software development, testing, and feedback.

To better understand the benefits of the model, Dhiman, K. L. (2024) has presented the advantages and disadvantages of the model as presented below:

Advantages of RAD Model

1. Flexible and adaptable to changes.
2. It is useful when you must reduce the overall project risk.
3. It is adaptable and flexible to changes.
4. Due to code generators and code reuse, there is a reduction of manual coding

Disadvantages of RAD Model

1. It cannot be used for smaller projects.
2. Not all applications is compatible with RAD.
3. When technical risk is high, it is not suitable.
4. Requires highly skilled designers or developers.

Recommendation in Incorporating Information Security using the NIST Cybersecurity Framework

Initiation Phase: During the requirements planning of RAD, the initiation of security requirements must commence, a detailed list of security concerns with regards to the gathering of data must be crafted, though there will be changes in the requirements it is acceptable since the model provides refinement during the prototyping stage. The data to be collected must be assured that it is handled properly during the development.

Acquisition/ Development Phase: This phase can be integrated in the user design phase, since it involves risk assessment. The difference with this in the waterfall model is that it will assess the security mostly in the prototyping stage which is actually efficient and productive since the all the possible risk, attacks, and vulnerabilities are identified before the actual construction of the whole program/ system. It is also a good avenue to refine the results of the assessment that will lead to the development of the information security plan or policy of the software.

Implementation/ Assessment Phase: This phase must be placed in the construction phase it is suggested that there is a formal documentation of all the results of the security check indicated in the risk assessment or in the plan developed. The results will depend on the testing and full construction of the software or program. Although testing of the plan and security measures where conducted in the prototyping stage, still in the full construction there will always be changes that is why full and careful documentation of all modules and their respective security measures must take place.

Operations/ Maintenance Phase: Since the RAD model has only minimal phases, the operations phase can be inserted together with the implementation since it involves change management and development of changes in the risk assessment and security policy.

Sunset/ Disposal Phase: The disposal phase or sunset is the cutover or the implementation and transition of the software. All data and information stated in the requirements planning will be recalled in this phase if it was treated properly. Like other models, the storage and transition of data is considered in this phase of the NIST framework. Although it is similar with other models, the process of storage, retrieval, and transition of data can be already formulated in the prototyping stage as there are modules that require database and a backend process where the transition of data is considered and only in the sunset phase the actual data transition, storage retrieval, archiving, and disposal is commenced. It will ensure a high valued security assessment.

V-MODEL

The V-Model provides a new perspective on dealing with business changes. The main concept of the model is that in every phase there is always a parallel testing. This model is a variation of the waterfall which is based on the interaction of each phase with testing stages. What highlights the model is that it promotes tenacity when implementing, a phase cannot move forward without the approval and testing of the existing phase to make sure that all changes or requests are addressed (Maryani, H. P., et al. 2022).

According to the study of Jagli, D., et al (2017), the V-Model poses strengths and weaknesses which are:

Advantages of V-Model

1. Success rate is more compared to waterfall model.
2. Saves time due to testing of planning and design work will be finished before coding.
3. Bugs are found at early stage.
4. Suitable for small projects

Disadvantages of V-Model

1. Least flexible with respect to modifications
2. Prototype of software is not available until implementation phase
3. In middle of project if any changes happens will effect changes for test documents as well as requirement documents.

Recommendation in Incorporating Information Security using the NIST Cybersecurity Framework

Initiation Phase: One of the strengths of the V Model is that in every phase there is a testing and acceptance phase equivalent (left-right model). Identifying the needed process, data, information, and other information security related areas are needed to be tested if all areas are correct and needed, after the identification the client of the requesting organization shall approved these areas. In addition, in this phase it can be also tested and ask for the approval of the organization regarding the assets needed to be considered in developing the system. Besides from the collection of data with regards to the actual system, the initiation phase must consider the security features of the system and on the other side (validation) is to validate if the prescribed security features meet the user requirements, needs, and expectations.

Acquisition/ Development Phase: During the System Design, a risk assessment can be developed. Since this phase involves results from the succeeding phase all the tested and approved security requirements are then used to develop a risk assessment and an information security plan. After its development, the assessment or plan is then tested and approved by the organization and is accepted as part of the development. The risk assessment shall provide an understanding of the possible security threats and solutions from acquiring the information system. This will help them to assess if what costs must be added and modules to consider in adding or revising to meet the demands of information security.

Implementation/ Assessment Phase: From the architectural design down to module design the implementation phase of the NIST framework can be integrated, however it differs the process since the actual coding and main programming is at the end of the model, the proposed security features can be then tested in this phases it has a similar approach with the RAD Model before delving into the main development testing is integrated in each phase. After each test the result is then reviewed and accepted by the organization. The V-Model also provides an avenue in this implementation phase to check if the modules of the system or features meet the security requirements and does not in any way conflict with the software requirements specifications by testing and validation.

Operations/ Maintenance Phase: During the coding phase where all security requirements are already tested and accepted, the development of the system must consider all the accepted security requirements and must undergo quality assurance and change management to assure that the system is not only functional, but is also secured from possible threats, attacks, and vulnerabilities which solutions are laid out in the security policy or requirements.

Sunset/ Disposal Phase: Since there is no provision in the V-Model that clearly states the transition, implementation, and storage of existing data to the proposed system, the researcher suggests that the disposal or sunset phase of the NIST cybersecurity framework is placed from the architectural down to Unit testing since it identifies the needs

of the system and security, the creation of the database and network is also considered in these phases which are crucial in data transition and storage.

SPIRAL MODEL

Confusions have been raised about the use of the spiral model amongst students, faculty, and practitioners. In the study of Singh, A., et al (2020). it explains a well detailed definition of the spiral model. It states that the spiral model develops software in incremental releases. On the first phases of the development a prototype is created before moving into the design and coding phase it ensures that the requirement or change is being met at each phase, after the development of the software the developers or the team must plan for the next phase. The spiral model is used when there is a limited budget and risk assessment is important, and importantly the model is used only for medium – high risk projects.

Despite of the confusions of the Spiral Model, Shylesh, S. (2017) has presented the advantages as well as the disadvantages of the use of the model;

Advantages of Spiral Model

1. Continuous changing requirements can be managed.
2. Much use of prototypes is allowed.
3. Requirements collect more accurately.
4. Users see the system early.
5. Development process is divided into parts and risky parts are developed early which help better management.

Disadvantages of Spiral Model

1. Complex management.
2. Project completion duration is not known.
3. Not suitable for low risky and small projects.
4. Process is complex.
5. Spiral indefinitely can go
6. Large number of phases requires heavy documentation.

Recommendation in Incorporating Information Security using the NIST Cybersecurity Framework

Initiation Phase: Spiral model was developed for the purpose of valuing risk assessment. Having the NIST framework shall strengthen its goal of crafting software where security is always a consideration. During the initiation, like the other models data, information, business process are all determined and all features of the software or project are scrutinized and well planned about what security features must be in place.

Acquisition/ Development Phase: The model shows the risk assessment of the study and how it is used. This already explains the advantage of the spiral model with other models in terms of information security.

Implementation/ Assessment Phase: All requirements stated in the planning are tested, the unique part of the spiral model is that the security feature requirements can be tested in prototype and the requirements may change during the development. With this, the security features and other parts of the system can be viewed by the client multiple times even during the development. Also, because the model is designed to address risk assessment, the risky parts of the software requirements are also divided into teams that address them quickly.

Operations/ Maintenance Phase: This phase can be integrated in the evaluation phase of the spiral model as it involves maintenance and assuring that all security requirements are met and changes during the development are addressed. Proper documentation of all experiences by the client during this phase should be well maintained. Since this is spiral, all of the comments and experiences of the client may undergo another requirements gathering which also means another cost for them.

Sunset/ Disposal Phase: Similar to the V-Model there is no direct phase in the Spiral Model that is dedicated to disposal, the researcher suggests that the disposal or sunset phase can be included in the evaluation or in the development, since this involves the actual data transition, proper storage, and archival.

AGILE MODEL

One of the most used and positively accepted methodology in the corporate world today is the agile methodology, in Islam, et al (2020) study it was highlighted that this methodology has five phases which are iteration, development phase, release phase, and production phase. This model addresses fast phasing changes in all sizes of project from small to complex. According to the authors, the model is used in extreme programming (XP), feature driven development, and adaptive software development. It only shows how adaptive the model is to changes and its capacity to adjust on complex projects. An agile model uses scrums or meetings in a short span of time to address issues directly.

In the study of Gurung, G., et al (2020) it was stated in their study the advantages and disadvantages of using the agile model which are;

Advantages of Agile Model

1. Working through Pair programming produce well written compact programs that have fewer errors as compared to programmers working alone.
2. It reduces the total development time of the whole project.
3. Customer representatives get the idea of updated software products after each iteration. Therefore, it is easy for him to change any requirement if needed.

Disadvantages of Agile Model

1. Due to lack of formal documents, it creates confusion and important decisions taken during different phases can be misinterpreted at any time by different team members.
2. Due to the absence of proper documentation, when the project completes and the developers are assigned to another project, maintenance of the developed project can become a problem.

Recommendation in Incorporating Information Security using the NIST Cybersecurity Framework

Initiation Phase: As one of the mostly used methodology as of today, it is highly recommended that Agile must integrate security on its model. For the initiation all requirements similar to other models such as data, information, requirements on software, hardware, peopleware, and firmware must be considered especially the security requirements. Since this is Agile changes may occur during the development of the system which is an advantage for agile methodology since change requirements is the reason for its development. Although the model is adoptable to change, the early detection of security measures and possible threats during the development will help the organization or client to minimize its cost by establishing a high-level information security policy throughout the development.

Acquisition/ Development Phase: All requirements identified in the former shall be built inside the iteration and sprint. The inclusion of risk assessment planning and development of security policies can be done in this form, during the design phase or the prototyping, initial risk assessment of each module or feature of the system can be identified, after the initial identification, the security personnel may proceed with the integration and suggest a plan where these attacks can be mitigated in the actual programming/ development (e.g. writing a code with algorithm to prevent SQL injection) and also suggest features in the system that will strengthen its security (ex.: 2 Factor Authentication, OCR, Email Verification, etc.) in this way the security is fully implemented in the system. After the development, is the test all security features must be tested to assure it meets the security requirements and to further improve the risk assessment and security policy when the system is implemented, deploy and review shall help in acquiring and changing the security requirements.

Implementation/ Assessment Phase: The implementation phase is highly suggested to be ingrained inside the iteration loop in the deployment and review with some of its functionalities also in the release phase. This will ensure if all security requirements are met and to assess if there are still needs to be improved.

Operations/ Maintenance Phase: Maintenance Phase of the agile model best suits the operations phase. Change is constant in the IT industry, that is the main reason why a full documentation of the deployment and maintenance phase is needed to address all

changes of the system and also the system's security. With the agile method it becomes more flexible to address all security changes.

Sunset/ Disposal Phase: In a similar vein with other SDLC models, the sunset or disposal phase can be ingrained in the last part of the model which is maintenance. Since the agile model provides flexibility in the iteration or sprint loop, the procedures of transition, archiving, storage and retrieval of data and information must all be tested before proceeding to the last phase where implementation is made.

Conclusions

The study revealed how each SDLC may possess and integrate the five phases of the NIST. Initiation phase reveals that all models receive the same analysis in data gathering and considering all information, data, and security requirements, the only difference is how it is maintained and passed on to the next phase of the model or in other phases. Also, in the study it is observed that not all models have the provision for data transition and disposal. This is the sunset or disposal phase which features the proper transition, disposal, archival, and retrieval of data. The analysis of SDLC models shows that it can be ingrained in some parts of the phases of all the models, this only shows that data acquisition and removal is a vital component of information security and must be taken into consideration by SDLCs.

Nevertheless, this analytical review of the different software development life cycle integrating information security provides a new perspective on using SDLC with security. Also, it is important to note that the used framework was the version 2 of the NIST framework which the researcher can conclude that it has used a new version contributing a new idea in the field of information security and software development. The analysis provides also technical skills on how each SDLC and security is used in different project size and showed the benefits it can provide to companies such as costs cutting, staff time reduction, and being safe with possible threats and attacks inside and outside of the organization.

Recommendations

With the results of the study, it is recommended that for future researchers that other software development life cycles such as the iterative waterfall, agile scrum and emerging SDLCs be subject as samples in integrating information security that would benefit their process. Also, it is recommended that the existing SDLC may add new phases that will deal with data transition, storage, archival, and disposal to accommodate the last phase of the NIST framework which is disposal. These recommendations will fully help project managers to understand the importance of information security and the advantages that it brings in terms of project development and economic purposes for the organization.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Although the research did not use any data gathering tool in collecting quantitative data, the research used documents and related literature in obtaining its objective. The researcher verified all sources and made sure that all sources are credible as majority of the research are all published internationally. Another compliance with ethical standard is that all studies and their authors are cited properly using the proper and new format of APA citation.

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